

Theoretical and Philosophical Article

Possible (Re)configurings of Mathematics and Mathematics Education through Drawing

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ABSTRACT: This paper offers a methodological alternative to drawing with/in mathematics by attuning to loving philosophies—agential realism and Indigenous philosophies through mathematics—to suggest drawing as a possible axio-onto-epistemology of mathematics that is expressed with one’s whole body, lived by human and other-than-human beings, and that is inseparable from aesthetics and ethics. Through this emerging possibility, this paper intends to highlight mathematics as in/determinately plural as well as the need for axiology, epistemology, and ontology to be lived as inseparable from each other with/in the field of mathematics education.

KEYWORDS: *drawing; mathematx; mathematics; agential realism; Indigenous Knowledges; loving philosophies*

There are myriad theoretical approaches and frameworks guiding the literature emerging from the field of mathematics education research. However, many of these approaches share the tendency towards categorizing, labeling, analyzing (in the sense of dissecting), and breaking continuities to discrete concepts or constructs. These approaches are often guided by representationalist approaches to knowledge² (Barad, 2003; see Figure 1). Because of the strong historical and philosophical ties of representationalism with colonization, however, the dominance of representationalist approaches has favored the imposition and reinforcement of dominant

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² Barad (2003) understands representationalism (see Figure 1) as “the belief in the ontological distinction between representations and that which they purport to represent; in particular, that which is represented is held to be independent of all practices of representing” (p. 804). A representationalist view of knowledge implies a break between epistemology and ontology—representations and reality. This view implies an understanding of epistemology as “the investigation of what distinguishes justified belief from opinion” (Million, 2015, p. 339). This understanding of epistemology, thus, posits reason and justification as *necessary*—rather than just one possible way—for knowledge to be ‘valid’ (Martin, 2017; Million, 2015). Thus, anything emerging from something other than rational justification is automatically undeserving of ‘valid knowledge’ recognition, creating in this way a clear divide between what can be considered valid knowledge and what cannot (Million, 2015; Santos, 2007). Accordingly, valid knowledge is understood to emerge *exclusively* through intellectual activity—through the mind—creating an epistemological break between mind and body. Through this understanding then, one’s body and lived experiences are forced out of one’s relationality with knowledge.

worldviews that rely on ‘othering,’ hierarchical notions of knowledge and being, and the erasure of the ‘other’³ (Bell, 2013; Cisneros Puebla, 2013; Fasheh, 2012; Gutiérrez, 2017; Martin, 2017; Million, 2015; Minh-ha, 1988; Santos, 2007; Tuck & Yang, 2014). This, in turn, has been understood as justification to silence and keep in the margins other ways of knowing and being—inflicting epistemic violence.⁴ As Million (2015) writes, “[S]ubjugating epistemologies that are nonhierarchical and nonhuman centered is not accomplished without violence. The violence of silencing is basic to the hegemony” (p. 340).

Moreover, the entanglement of mathematics education research with conventional and territorializing⁵ ontologies of mathematics exacerbates the epistemic damage emergent from the field. As the notion of mathematics as a “universal language” (Ross, 2015) continues to have currency, the entanglements of mathematics ontology and epistemology with Platonism,⁶ formalism,⁷ and an Aristotelian view of ‘truth’—the understanding that a statement is either true

³ The clear break between what is and what is not valid knowledge that is entailed in the dominant Western understanding of epistemology through representationalism has fueled, and still fuels, an ideology of superiority from which any other way of knowing the world is ‘sub-human’ and, thus, erasable. Santos (2007) calls this dichotomous understanding of knowledge *abyssal thinking*. He traces the creation of “the truly abyssal lines” (p. 49) to the mid sixteenth century when disputes among European countries regarding their colonies required a clear demarcation of ‘one side of the line’ and ‘the other side of the line’ to settle territorial conflicts. These abyssal lines were correspondingly drawn in the realm of knowledge as well:

Again, the colonial zone is, *par excellence*, the realm of incomprehensible beliefs and behaviors which in no way can be considered knowledge, whether true or false. The other side of the line harbors only incomprehensible magical or idolatrous practices. The utter strangeness of such practices led to denying the very human nature of the agents of such practices. On the basis of their refined conceptions of humanity and human dignity, the humanists reached the conclusion that the savages were sub-human (p. 51, emphasis in original)

⁴ The assumed superiority of the colonizer’s way of knowing validated the violence and destruction inflicted on beings—human and more-than-human (Gutiérrez, 2017)—who fell on ‘the other side of the line.’ Santos (2007) follows abyssal thinking (see footnote 2) from the mid sixteenth century to current understandings of knowledge, highlighting that the dominant Western sense of epistemology is just a continuation of these violent practices of invisibilization—where modern science, philosophy, and theology are now on one side of the line, and “[o]n the other side of the line, there is no real knowledge; there are beliefs, opinions, intuitive or subjective understandings, which, at the most, may become objects or raw materials for scientific inquiry” (p. 47).

⁵ I use the term “territorializing” (Deleuze & Guattari, 1987) to emphasize how rigid and almost unmovable these understandings of mathematics have become—like heavy, ossified structures obstructing the flow of waters coming from different places, with different cadences and material histories.

⁶ Through a Platonist view, mathematical objects exist in a different world outside of the one in which we live and are independent of our realities (Gillies, 2015; Peck, 2018; Paul, 2020). These mathematical objects and structures are understood to be purely objective and universally true since they transcend context, space, and time. Ontologically, then, mathematics is constituted of ideals that exist in a different realm “which cannot be perceived by any of the usual five bodily senses”, and hence, the mind is the only medium through which one “can gain knowledge of the world of forms [where mathematical objects exist]” (Gillies, 2015, p. 148). This view of mathematics continues to influence how mathematics and doers of mathematics are perceived—“mathematicians have the reputation of being external to any trace of reality” (Paul, 2020, p. 3)—and how mathematical activity is considered as exclusively intellectual. Moreover, it contributes to the perception of mathematics as a static, pre-existing body of knowledge one arrives to or discovers through the intellect. Epistemologically, this implies that the only way to know mathematics is through the mind. Additionally, the belief that mathematics is transcendental and objective has favored the understanding of individuals through the ideal of a ‘universal learner.’ That is, since mathematics is understood as universal and objective, individuals are perceived as undifferentiated objects—‘containers’—ready to acquire universally-applicable mathematics—ignoring in this way all subjectivities (Burton, 1995/2008; Jacobs, 2010; Peck, 2018).

⁷ Through formalism, mathematics is understood as a set of theorems one arrives at by playing with symbols as one follows a determined set of rules that adhere to Aristotelian logic (Ernest, 1991). Through this perspective, then, mathematical activity is restricted to symbolic manipulations that start from a set of axioms and that lead to mathematical truths through deductive reasoning. There is often a shared belief that any mathematical truth can be represented by a formal system as long as one chooses the appropriate set of axioms and rules to follow within Aristotelian logic. Thus, through this lens, mathematics is the symbols and rules that one defines mathematics to be

or false, never both—are now not only sequestering different mathematics in the Western world, but also in the world at large. As a result, different ways of knowing and being that occur outside these territorializing entanglements are being invisibilized through the “myth of one and only one kind of mathematics” (Fasheh, 2012, p. 94) and the view that they are the only way to ‘progress’⁸—or, for that matter, that progress is itself the assumed telos.

Figure 1. “Knowledge through representationalism.” From *In-Betweens* [comic], by S. Abreu, 2020, p. 22.

and, hence, does not exist outside of language. However, the notion that every mathematical truth can be formalized into an axiomatic system has already been refuted by Gödel’s (1931) Incompleteness Theorems, one of which shows that no system following Aristotelian logic is complete. Put differently, one can only prove ‘all mathematical truths’ within an inconsistent system—a system that allows a statement to be both true and false. Thus, limiting mathematics to just what can be fitted into a formal system automatically excludes a richness of mathematical knowledge and practices that cannot be formalized. Formalism, nonetheless, continue to be influential in how mathematics is taught at universities and has led to equating mathematical activity to deduction (Wertheim, 2019). This view of mathematics has centered proofs as key to the epistemology of mathematics, leading to the narrow view that mathematics emerges through a purely deductive process—where axioms are chosen and theorems emerge as logical conclusions of those axioms.

⁸ Million (2015) argues that the dominance of Western epistemology has been perpetuated through the denial of its historical roots and through the positing of indigenous knowledge as its categorical opposite through “an evolutionary schema, into a past that always denotes primitive. Contemporary scientific knowledge must purport its superiority as the newest and most innovative against an indigenous knowledge forever posited as its contrary” (p. 339). In resonance, Mignolo (2011) uses the term *modernity* to refer to the framing of dominant Western knowledge systems as “the newest and most innovative.” He understands modernity as a “celebratory rhetoric...the rhetoric of salvation and newness, based in European achievements during the Renaissance” (p. 6) which include capitalism as a new economic model and the scientific revolution. He defines modernity as “a complex narrative whose point of origination was Europe; a narrative that builds Western civilization by celebrating its achievements *while hiding at the same time its darker side*” (pp. 2–3, emphasis added). Through this narrative, ‘universal knowledge’—that is, knowledge whose validity is understood to be independent from context—is framed as the ultimate ‘path to progress’ since ‘reason’ is posited as the ultimate achievement of Western economic and epistemic systems. Through this framing of knowledge, then, dominant mathematics becomes the pinnacle of ‘true’ and desirable knowledge as it becomes the ultimate way to ‘break away’ from the complexities of bodies—from lived experience—, hence fueling territorializing claims about its ‘objectivity’ and ‘universality.’

Aligned with this view, researchers in the field of mathematics education often take the philosophical assumptions underlying conventional ontologies and epistemologies of mathematics for granted—presumed to be shared and accepted by all mathematics educators—and, hence, not explicitly stated. The normative practice is to demand that new theories articulate their ontological, epistemological, and axiological assumptions, while old theories are exempted (Walter & Anderson, 2013). The lack of philosophical questionings of the forces guiding the field of mathematics education research, however, has contributed to ignoring—either purposefully or unintentionally—or justifying the epistemic violence entailed in prominent academic approaches to knowledge. This damage is not merely ideological; it is very much material⁹ (Lenz Taguchi, 2012). As Fasheh (2012) writes through his experience in Palestine,

Gradually, I realized that the [dominant Western] mathematics I studied and taught suppressed and won over my mother’s mathematics through bullying; by devaluing, ignoring, and belittling her mathematics, and providing instead another mathematics that claimed to be neutral and universal—the only path into the future. It won not because it is superior or better but through being a tool serving interests of dominant political and economic powers, helping them in controlling people, suppressing their knowledges, and robbing them of what they have (including their biological abilities). ... In contrast to my mathematics, which was aloof, my mother’s mathematics was embedded in life like salt in food; we can taste it but not see it. (p. 94)

It is important to highlight that colonization is not a far past (Yang, 2017). It is a continuing force that keeps conquering other knowledges as well as ways of being, and mathematics education continues to act as a colonizing force¹⁰ (Doolittle & Glanfield, 2007).

Thus, it is important for me to unearth the philosophical assumptions guiding territorializing ontologies and epistemologies of mathematics as well as representationalist approaches to knowledge¹¹ to both show that different assumptions can be made and to foreground that these

⁹ Mignolo (2011) argues that “hidden behind the rhetoric of modernity, economic practices dispensed with human [and more-than-human] lives, and *knowledge justified racism and the inferiority of human [and more-than-human] lives that were naturally considered dispensable*” (p. 6, emphasis added). That is, through modernity (see footnote 7), the understanding of valid knowledge as strictly a product of reason and rationality was framed, and continues to be so, as the ultimate achievement of Western civilization which, in turn, is used to justify who is dispensable and who is not depending on where they fall in the hierarchy of ‘intelligence,’—and thus the violence and oppression inflicted on them. Modernity, thus, emerges as a narrative to not only aggrandize Western civilization—including its ways of knowing—, but also to hide the violent logic behind it. As a result, any harm inflicted on others seems inevitable and even natural. Mignolo names this *underlying logic* behind modernity *coloniality* and argues that “[t]here is no modernity without coloniality” (p. 3). This violent logic has led to the devaluation and invisibilization of modes of knowing that are relational, felt, and generated in lived experience by arguing that they are not ‘objective’ or are ‘non-mathematics’ since they don’t refer to the imaginary of ideology and representation (Gutiérrez, 2017).

¹⁰ As Doolittle (2007) states:

Indigenous culture has ancient, powerful ways of understanding the world, ways that are sophisticated and strong enough to have enabled the people to survive since creation. But those ways of understanding may actually be supplanted by mathematics education, which is not just mere knowledge, but a Trojan horse full of Greek philosophers wielding *Logos*. (p. 28, emphasis in original)

¹¹ The ontological separation between knowledge and lived experience assumed by representationalism is particularly active in territorializing/conventional views of mathematics through which mathematics is understood as abstracted/abstractable. Specifically, mathematics is perceived as either 1) independent/separated from the real world in Platonism, 2) detachable/abstractable relations from the real world in traditional realisms, 3) symbols and objects that do not exist outside of language in formalism/nominalism, or 4) constructed structures that live exclusively in the mind in constructivism (de Freitas, 2017a, 2018). These understandings entail that mathematical knowledge is only obtainable through intellectual activity, and thus, have left the body and matter out of—even paralyzed them from—doing and knowing mathematics. I argue, moreover, that through colonizing understandings of knowledge, the assumed separation of mathematics from reality has granted the discipline the ‘status’ of ‘purely objective’ or ‘universal.’

have significant political and material consequences. But these assumptions do not come to us ready-made; they are not always intentional choices that we make—theories sometimes choose us, or affect us. Understanding our assumptions—and sharing them with colleagues—may often require tracing the values and desires that move through us.

In particular, both Barad and Gutiérrez speak to very personal wounds. Growing up immersed in a world that deeply believed in the narrative of modernity, in science as the *only* path towards progress, in turning Mexico into the US or Europe as the only way to ‘save’ it, I convinced myself of these same narratives by shutting down vital and profound feelings/sensings that were telling me otherwise. I grew up learning that if my thoughts/feelings deviated from ‘rationality,’ from how academics—particularly Western and male—thought about or understood the world, then I *should* correct my perceptions in order for me to be better, worthy, valuable, in order for me to be deserving within this society. Trying to change my ways of knowing and being to ones that aligned more with what I was learning as more valuable, thus, I started to disconnect myself from understandings that were felt, that were bodily, like my relationality with drawing—it became ‘just a hobby’ rather than a very intimate way for me to connect with the world and myself—and from my understandings of everything as living, magical, continuous, and inseparable since I was learning to relate with the world as if it were a dissected, lifeless body. I had to continuously tell myself that my feelings of interconnectedness with a living world were at most ‘metaphorical,’ maybe ‘poetic,’ but not *real*; the only truth can only come from reason. I, thus, gradually distanced myself from vital desires and feelings as I convinced myself I was getting closer to ‘pure’ knowledge through dominant mathematics. The harm that I was causing to myself, to others, however, was very real, and I ended up in dark places from which I have gradually gotten out of through unlearning (insidiously) violent practices and thanks to reconnecting lovingly with family, friends, feminist texts, and a living world.

When I first heard the term ‘epistemic violence,’ thus, it connected very deeply with personal wounds. The more I read texts that elaborated on this term, the more I sensed the various forces that had led me to harm myself in my attempts to become ‘more rational,’ to follow the unforgiving rhythms of a colonizing world even if they were dissonant to mine. The epistemic violence referred to in this paper, thus, emerges not only through the texts cited but also through marks on my own body—different but reverberating. Thus, when I first read Barad (2003) and Gutiérrez (2017), amongst myriad other authors—e.g., Audre Lorde, bell hooks, Gloria Anzaldúa, María-Milagros Rivera Garreta, la Librería de Mujeres de Milán, Sara Ahmed, Donna Haraway, Karen Barad, Nathalie Loveless, Terry Tempest Williams, the list goes on—, several of whom were introduced to me by my loving sister, Mariana, to whom I am deeply grateful, I felt like I was being hugged. Here were beautiful people telling me that my pain and feeling of inadequacy within this world was not a sign of my worthlessness but a manifestation of how a colonizing world inflicts violence on bodies. And they were telling me, “Don’t worry, there are other ways; there are loving ways.”

Barad’s agential realism was a balm for the deep cuts I have had to make to my understandings when presented with dominant notions of knowledge as discretely separable into concepts, systems, clearly defined hierarchies of life, disciplines—separations to which I could never fully relate. Barad’s understanding of knowing as inseparable from becoming, as continuous, open, and dynamic felt like finally being able to breathe after continuously being pulled underwater as Barad presented me a way to express vital continuities within academic spaces that insist on discretizing (e.g., coding) as the only way to ‘produce valid research.’

At the same time, Gutiérrez (2017) connected with my desire to express not only continuities but also my intense feeling that mathematics could be so much more than what I was being allowed to live as mathematics within academic spaces—to reconnect with my intuition that mathematics

could be open, more than symbols, embodied, relational, more than human. Reading Gutiérrez, thus, felt like I was reading my heart through her words. Her words were singing something I have been longing to hear for more than two decades: My relationship with mathematics, drawing, and a living world is real and valuable. How I lived/sensed the world was also *knowing*, it was not just a ‘figurative’ or ‘metaphorical’ understanding of it; it was valid, true, and powerful in its own right.

As the length of my paper was getting unwieldy, however, and acknowledging that there is literature describing the different philosophical foundations of predominant approaches to mathematics—e.g., Platonism, conventional realisms,¹² constructivism,¹³ formalism—, I decided through Nathalie’s (reviewer) and Alex’s (editor) advice to, rather than recount ideas that have been presented elsewhere—which runs the risk of conferring upon them some kind of originating position, which I then seek to replace with a new and better approach—as the first half of my paper, to instead explicitly voice that unearthing the philosophical forces entangled with territorializing notions of mathematics and knowledge, as well as their historical ties, directly impacted and shaped my own understandings and urgency for loving methodologies, and, in turn, the way in which I engaged with this paper. I also decided to turn what was previously the beginning of my paper into a rain of footnotes throughout this introduction. Through understanding both the philosophical assumptions of conventional notions of mathematics and knowledge as well as their historical ties to colonizing interests, I was able to reconnect with drawing as a node of knowing, relating, and becoming that was close to me when I was a kid—an understanding that I was taught to fracture and devalue, and that now needs to heal.

I, thus, offer an alternative methodology to drawing with/in mathematics that focuses on *dynamism*, *continuities*, and *indeterminacy*—guided by my understandings of feminist new materialisms and Indigenous Knowledges, which offer strong theories to (re)open one’s perception to

¹² In structural and Aristotelian realisms mathematics exists in the material world. For structural realism, mathematics exists in the underlying structures and relations of the world (Madrid Casado, 2008), and for Aristotelian realism, mathematics is embodied by the world (Gillies, 2015). However, the notion of objectivity and universality of mathematics is still present since mathematical structures are understood as faithful representations or reflections of the inherent structures of the world and, hence, universal truths independent of the human mind (Madrid Casado, 2008). This view of mathematics leads to the framing of the discipline as the only way towards a true and complete understanding of the world since mathematical representations are believed to be isomorphic to the structures of the world—i.e., as having the exact same relations, structures, and properties as the world. Thus, mathematics—and therefore science—are viewed as “the way the world works” (Thomas, 1996, p. 13), and, thus, the only way to know the world ‘objectively,’ according to this view, is through mathematics. Moreover, under these realisms, mathematics is not mathematics without a process of abstraction—or extraction—of these relations from the world: “Mathematics is not ‘about’ human activity, phenomena, or science. It is about the extractions and formalizations of ideas—and their manifold consequences” (Mac Lane, 1986, as cited by Thomas, 1996, p. 15). This reductive view of mathematical activity as abstraction/extraction guides various essentialist arguments about what should and should not be considered mathematics (e.g., Thomas, 1996; Hickman & Huckstep, 2003) and continues to push aside the possibility of any alternative by either “rendering it invisible or defining it as error or as nonmathematics” (Bloor, 1991, p. 180). However, as Lakoff and Núñez (2000) note, these beliefs compose a mythology of the nature of mathematics—what they called the “Romance of Mathematics”—that “helps to maintain an elite and then justify it” (p. 341). The influence of structural realism can be seen among the component beliefs of this mythology, particularly in the belief that “[m]athematics has an objective existence, providing structure to this universe and any possible universe, *independent of and transcending the existence of human beings or any beings at all*” (p. xv, emphasis added).

¹³ Constructivist theories of learning are usually the base for the notion of mathematics as an ongoing construction of concepts that occurs inside the learner’s mind (von Glasersfeld, 1983/2008), which has dominated in the field of mathematics education (de Freitas, 2018). Constructivist theories are often guided by either Piaget or Vygotsky’s work, the main difference between the two being where concept construction begins. For the former, concept formations “begin with the actions of the individual and are then shared out in the social realm, while for the latter, scientific concepts begin in the social realm and are internalized by the individual” (de Freitas, 2017a, p. 4). Either way, through a constructivist lens, mathematical objects and concepts are immaterial—either cognitive constructions and schemes that live exclusively inside the mind or immaterial concepts that are internalized.

continuities as well as to acknowledge and lovingly tend to them. From new materialisms I focus on Barad's (2003) *agential realism* and from Indigenous Knowledges on Gutiérrez's (2017) *mathematx* as powerful and loving methodological alternatives to violent approaches to 'knowledge production' in mathematics education research in order to suggest drawing as a possible axio-onto-epistemology of mathematics. I will also express why the convergence of all these understandings makes sense to me and how I perceive their resonances. I conclude with possibilities that might be (re)opened within mathematics and mathematics education research through drawing.

As Nathalie beautifully expresses: *There is much about this paper that feels like weaving. Given the re-visioning of the re-viewer as an intra-viewer, who is therefore invited to move from the evaluative outside to the participative and responsive inside, the paper becomes a weaving together of voices and ideas. It is different from co-authorship though, which often become univocal. But there is also the weaving together of theories—the two threads of thought are carefully handled so as to respect their differences and independence and to produce something that exceeds the sum of the parts. Additionally, like in Jorrot and Roth's (2018) description of weaving, the fabric that is the outcome of the weaving process is not just determined by the individual threads, nor even the intentionality of the weaver. Indeed, the threads themselves exert a force that constrains the weaver. The weaver must push and pull, but also learn to succumb. She must treat the threads with care, and this is part of the way of working, the methodological commitments, that produces compelling textile. One commitment relates to the use of language, which carries with it so much oppressive force.*

The Violence of Language in Mathematics Education

Language has been instrumental in the framing of humans as superior to other beings, which in turn, has helped justify violence against more-than-human persons. Moreover, the overemphasis on language in mathematics education has contributed to the perception that mathematics is an exclusively human and intellectual activity. However, Wertheim (2019) argues that more-than-human entities are doers of mathematics as well: "From the subatomic particles to cosmological spacetime, and at every scale in between, we find natural things *doing* mathematics" (p. 71). This notion presents an alternative perception of mathematics: one of mathematics as a performative activity rather than just a symbolic or language-centered one. To elaborate on this idea, she considers music. Just like mathematics, music can be written down in terms of symbols on a sheet of paper. However, in music, being able to write one's music on a music sheet is not central to being a musician. Rather, a musician is someone who *plays* music: "The possibility of writing music down is something apart from its recital—the notation isn't the act" (p. 71). Similarly, she argues that one does not need to know symbolic mathematics to *play* mathematics:

Just as music is quintessentially a performance, so we might say that things are *performing* mathematics. In this way of seeing, it makes no more sense to say that an electron calculates the outcome of a Schrödinger equation than to say that Jimi Hendrix was playing a musical score. Hendrix, who also couldn't read music, could play it at a superlative level. Things in the world, such as atoms, are like Hendrix with his guitar: while illiterate they perform complex mathematics across a wide range of many different subfields. ... They aren't manipulating symbols or calculating equations; rather they are performing mathematical riffs. (p. 71, emphasis in original)

Thus, Wertheim (2019) argues that viewing mathematics as a performance "enables us to recalibrate our relationship with the subject, reframing it as a mode of engagement in which we can highlight its joyous potential for all people" (p. 70)—instead of utilizing it as a tool for domination and exclusion.

As important as it is to liberate our understanding of knowledge from its linguistic cage, it is also important to problematize the current dominant languages driving ‘knowledge production’ in the fields of mathematics and mathematics education. In particular, Barton and Frank (2001) argue that the key to different mathematics lies “embedded within the very grammar” (p. 136) of the language used in mathematics since “speakers of languages which are different structurally and grammatically are led to different ways of construing the world” (p. 135). English, for example, is a noun-centric language, and, thus, “[w]e talk of mathematical objects because that is what the English language makes available for talking, but it is just a way of talking” (Barton, 2008, p. 127). Nominalization in mathematics—the turning of actions into nouns in order to perform other actions—is an example of the power that language has in shaping/restricting how we engage with mathematics. However, many Indigenous languages have a verb-rich structure which allows for an understanding of the relationships among entities in the world as in constant flux. For example, Henderson (2000) writes about Mi’kmaq—the language of the Mi’kmaw community in Canada—in the following way:

The use of verbs rather than a plethora of noun subjects and objects is important: it means that very few fixed and rigid separate objects exist in the Mi’kmaq worldview (or landscape). What they consider instead is great flux, eternal transformation and interconnected space. (p. 264)

Borden (2011) thus wonders, “What would happen if we drew upon the grammatical structures of Mi’kmaq instead of English” (p. 11)? Moreover, Barton and Frank (2001) argue that “the sort of knowing which results from having two or more world-views is a deeper, more aware sort of knowing than that which results from having only one” (p. 146), and, thus,

to restrict thinking to the patterns merely of English... is to lose a power of thought which, once lost, can never be regained. ... Western culture has made, through language, a provisional analysis of reality and, without correctives, holds resolutely to that analysis as final. The only correctives lie in all those other tongues which by aeons of independent evolution have arrived at different, but equally logical, provisional analyses. (Whorf, 1956, as cited by Barton & Frank, 2001, p. 147)

I wonder then, what if we opened up our expressivities and understandings of mathematics to not just more than one language, but to drawing—not as an act of representing but as a performance, “as a mode of engagement in which we can highlight its joyous potential for all people” (Wertheim, 2019, p. 70)—and to the inseparable agencies materializing the universe?

Predominant Understandings of Drawing in Mathematics Education Research

It is important to note that the forces of representationalism are still highly influential in theoretical understandings of drawing within mathematics education research. Moreover, mathematics education researchers tend to discuss drawings as *accessory* to various activities that are regarded as essential in learning mathematics—e.g., communicating one’s thinking, reasoning/thinking through mathematical ideas, visualizing/representing abstract concepts, and explaining complicated ideas—even if through various theoretical frameworks. For example, various researchers have approached students’ drawings as external representations of the student’s internal, mental configurations (e.g., Carlsen, 2009; Edens & Potter, 2007; Goldin & Kaput, 1996; MacDonald, 2013; Maschietto & Bartolini Bussi, 2008; Woleck, 2001). Through these approaches, researchers conceptualize drawings as a way of assessing what students know and a

means of investigating how they make meaning of mathematical ideas. This conceptualization, thus, foregrounds the *researcher's* judgement/interpretation of a student's drawing as 'insight' into the student's thinking. Mathematics education researchers have also viewed drawings as tools/inscriptions to communicate one's thinking and auxiliary in explaining ideas (e.g., Anderson et al., 2015; Arcavi, 2003; Carlsen, 2009; O'Halloran, 2015; Roth & McGinn, 1998). Other researchers have also understood drawings as mediators or support in constructing/internalizing new knowledge or bridging informal representations of mathematics to formal mathematical symbolism (e.g., Anderson et al., 2015; Arcavi, 2003; Carruthers & Worthington, 2006; Davis & Hyun, 2005; Edens & Potter, 2007; Lehrer et al., 2000; MacDonald, 2013; Maschietto & Bartolini Bussi, 2008; O'Halloran, 2015; Wyndham & Säljö, 1997). This view is strongly tied to the notion of drawings as an extension of thinking or mediator in reasoning. Drawings also tend to be framed as a way to 'visualize' or 'concretize' otherwise abstract and immaterial mathematical objects (e.g., Anderson et al., 2015; Arcavi, 2003; Carlsen, 2009; Davis & Hyun, 2005; Duval, 1999; Lehrer et al., 1999; O'Halloran, 2015; Rivera, 2014; Wright, 2012)—such as sets and functions.

Throughout this literature, several terms are used to define and frame drawings according to specific considerations and theoretical perspectives, most of them referring to them as some form of representation, visualization, or tool (e.g., Arcavi, 2003; Davis & Hyun, 2005; Duval, 1999; Edens & Potter, 2007; MacDonald, 2013; O'Halloran, 2015; Rivera, 2014). However, regardless of which of these terms is used, it is implied that drawings are a substitute for something else (Thom & McGarvey, 2015)—that is, a proxy for either otherwise imperceptible mathematical objects or for ideas in one's mind. This entails an ontological distinction between a drawing and what it is intended to represent. Moreover, the perceived externalization associated to the act of drawing has contributed to the understanding of drawings as mediating 'artefacts' or 'tools' in meaning-making (e.g., Carlsen, 2009; Maschietto & Bartolini Bussi, 2008).

Additionally, it is a common understanding that acts of representation—both internal and external—are essential to mathematical activity. Goldin and Kaput (1996) state that "internal imagistic representation is essential to virtually all mathematical insight and understanding" (p. 415), and Carlsen (2009) writes that "[t]o learn mathematics is to learn to produce and handle inscriptions for multiple purposes" (p. 59). These notions, however, are deeply intertwined with conventional ontologies of mathematics—e.g., the common understanding of representations as the only medium to access or perceive mathematical objects carries a Platonist notion of mathematics through which mathematical objects are nonexistent in our material reality, and the understanding of mathematics as working with inscriptions is tied to formalism and nominalism which reduce mathematical activity to operations on symbols. All of these understandings, present in different ways throughout most of this literature, contribute to the perception that mathematical activity is primarily an intellectual one where drawings and diagrams are merely aiding tools. Furthermore, drawing is framed as an intermediary activity towards a preset endpoint—e.g., learning power series (Carlsen, 2009), whole number operations (Rivera, 2014), perspective (Maschietto & Bartolini Bussi, 2008)—and, thus, conventional perceptions of what constitutes mathematics are left untroubled.

Moreover, as discussed previously, drawings are often perceived as representations of something else—usually of a mathematical object or a mental image—even if approached through different theoretical perspectives. This tendency resonates with what Barad (2003) perceives as the overpowering influence of representationalism in research: "The linguistic turn, the semiotic turn, the interpretive turn, the cultural turn: it seems that at every turn lately every 'thing'—even materiality—is turned into a matter of language or some other form of cultural representation" (p. 801). The overemphasis on representations and language in what constitutes research and

knowledge has contributed to the belief that they are the only way to access the world—either to create it or to know it. This belief has resulted in “the knowing subject...[being] enmeshed in a thick web of representations such that the mind cannot see its way to objects that are forever out of reach and all that is visible is the sticky problem of humanity’s own captivity within language” (pp. 811–812). Seeing drawings through this “thick web of representations,” thus, has limited our perception of drawing as just another form of representing.

Through this paper, however, I argue that the act of drawing, when understood through Barad’s (2003) agential realism and Gutiérrez’s (2017) *matemática*,¹⁴ can help one (re)sensitize oneself to other possible expressivities and relationalities with/in mathematics, mathematics education, and the world that are non-hierarchical, non-human centric, and that embrace indeterminacy, the virtual, and love.

The Interstitial Space where Agential Realism and Indigenous Knowledges Meet with/in Me

It is important to foreground that Barad’s ideas are not new nor exclusively a movement in Western philosophies; rather, resonating ideas have been central to various Indigenous Knowledges since generations before colonization but have been kept in the margins (Cannella & Manuelito, 2008). However, these ideas are gaining presence in this field mainly through Western researchers. The emergence of this paper is an example of this, as I started writing it inspired by Barad’s agential realism, and it was not until later that I became aware that resonating ideas have been present in Indigenous theories since way before but have been intentionally silenced, favoring the narrative of modernity. It is also important to acknowledge, however, that this does not mean that one can be reduced to the other since each emerges from, and carries with them, their own historical and material forces which guide them in different ways and through different—even if resonating—desires, understandings, and relationalities with/in the world. Thus, as they converge, they also diverge.

Acknowledging the complexity of their entanglements, I sense—as an over-washing wave—agential realism as emerging from the desire to tend to the so many epistemological, axiological, ontological, material fractures that representationalism has inflicted on bodies through dominant and colonizing worldviews. However, precisely because of its historical and material entanglements, given the dominance of Western epistemic systems and the abstraction of knowledge from Indigenous Wisdoms without consideration of the philosophies they are embedded in as a continuation of colonization (Mohanty, 2003; Visvanathan, 2007), I believe that it is paramount to not only foreground that despite the violent imposition of colonizing worldviews, Indigenous Wisdoms have held on, nurtured, lovingly protected, and embodied various of these continuities which have been fractured by dominant epistemologies, but to also engage with Indigenous Knowledges wholeheartedly, responsibly, and with willingness to be

¹⁴ I wanted to weave in the beautiful comment that Nathalie wrote here as she re-viewed this paper:

It struck me, as I read on, how these two people/concepts are definitely main threads, but there’s so much fraying that goes on as they gather momentum through the words and ideas of other people/concepts. It has me thinking about spatial imaginaries. As you perhaps know, Deleuze and Guattari were very much against trees because, as a spatial imaginary for knowing/being/etc., they carry assumptions about hierarchy, structure (through the central trunks), upward growth (progress), etc. That’s why they turned to rhizomes, which are decentralized, non-hierarchical, etc. If I were to visualize (draw?) your thinking here, there are certainly central nodes (Barad and Gutiérrez), but also lots of connecting lines, even to each other, that is more like a connected graph than like a tree. *Maybe the diffraction is the idea that new nodes can always be created—that these people/concepts do not create a contained space, but instead are generative of new spaces.* (Nathalie Sinclair, July 26, 2022, personal communication, emphasis added)

accountable for when one's engagement is hurtful, even if unintendedly. Accordingly, I am aware that my intentions and how I engage with these philosophies have the potential to become problematic, as it feels like that to me in waves as well. However, even if working with both philosophies together often creates strong tensions, choosing one over the other not only feels like a reification of abyssal thinking (Santos, 2007), but also feels disingenuous and in dissonance to the possibilities that these theories have reattuned me to.

In particular, trying to organize the ways in which I have related with these agencies, I sense agential realism as a force that reopened me to other possibilities—that showed my grounding to be shaky—while Indigenous Knowledges reassured me that there was rich soil where to re-braid my roots. Because I sense these theoretical stances as generative together, however, both these theories have *inseparably* offered me a strong theoretical stance through which to perceive and live the world differently. As I engage with both philosophies, they blend into each other and into me. At the same time, each resonates with my own histories, materialities, wounds, desires in their own way and with their own rhythms and expressivities. Both agential realism and Indigenous Knowledges have provided me forces through which to explore beautiful continuities and flows and continue to guide me in tending to them kindly and lovingly—each through their own histories and materialities while still transforming each other.

Thus, while I sense the tensions that emerge from engaging with these together, I also sense a generative resonance between the two—similar but different, entangled but differentiated, both in/as Nepantla—as their encounter feels familiar, reverberating with forces that have shaped, and continuously shape, me. Being from Mexico City, both Western-colonizing and Indigenous forces, among a myriad of other forces, have inseparably shaped my city, my family, and myself. They have been waves that crash into each other—together becoming something that is neither one nor the other while being inseparably both—and that crystalize and erode the materiality of my city and my country, living with/in me. Thus, their encounter with/in me feels familiar, both fitting and problematic.

As these forces converge and diverge with/in me, they create something that is neither one nor the other nor additively both. Rather, they diffract; they generate, and emerge as, something different as they encounter each other, transform each other—something that cannot be subsumed into a single one nor cleanly dissected into two. Accordingly, this paper and I have been and are continuously and inseparably transformed through the reverberations of these philosophies, as well as tensions and possible contradictions—willing to be accountable for when our expressivities emerge as harmful, even if unintendedly.

Thus, guided by the generative tensions across these multiple forces, this paper emerges from/as a dynamic in-between, a (re)configuring of the world, a (re)organization of matter—including my own matter—, as I reconnect with other ways to relate with knowing, becoming, sensing, the world, my own body. I feel it is important to acknowledge and present work emerging from places of tension as they are part of one's becoming. Guided by Nepantla—on which I elaborate later in this paper—, thus, I am inhabiting these tensions, this discomfort, these contradictions, hoping to birth new materialities and understandings. Like Leroy Little Bear (2000) writes: “No one has a pure worldview that is 100 percent Indigenous or Eurocentric; rather, everyone has an integrated mind, a fluxing and ambidextrous consciousness, a precolonized consciousness that flows into a colonized consciousness and back again” (p. 85).

Drawing with/in Mathematx—Mathematx with/in Drawing—through Mathematx-Indigenous Wisdoms-Agential Realism

In this section, I elaborate on how drawing and mathematics can be differently understood through the diffraction—“the result of the superposition of waves” (Barad, 2007, p. 74)—of Barad’s (2003) *agential realism* and Gutiérrez’s (2017) notion of *mathematx*, as well as resonating notions from Indigenous Knowledges. These theories allow for the exploration of continuities that through representationalism are often fractured into dichotomies—e.g., inside/outside the body, ontology/epistemology, subject/object, art/mathematics. Given my focus on drawings with/in mathematics and mathematics education research, I discuss how these theories offer a radical departure from the theoretical understanding of drawings as representations in mathematics and mathematics education research as well as from territorializing ontologies/epistemologies of mathematics.

In particular, in trying to organize how *mathematx* and *agential realism* have each transformed my understandings and relationality with/in drawing, four main notions emerge: drawing can be understood/perceived as 1) a dynamic performance open to knowing through expressing reciprocity, experiencing joy and connection, as well as through emerging patterns and mathematical forces through *mathematx*; 2) a dynamic and indeterminate practice, with no pre-established end, with/in which matter and knowledge are inseparably active participants and are continuously transformed and (re)configured; 3) a “threshold between the actualized and virtual” (de Freitas, 2016, p. 188) allowing oneself to (re)sensitize to non-linearity; 4) as *Nepantla*—as a site of multiple realities and healing. Braided into the fabric of these sections, I also discuss both how these understandings can (re)attune one to new possibilities through relating differently with/in drawing while at the same time how drawing can help one get closer to these same understandings—these understandings and drawing co-constituting each other.

Drawing as a Dynamic and Loving Performance through *Mathematx*

Gutiérrez (2017) turns to her Chicanx and Rarámuri roots and is guided by Indigenous epistemologies to offer an alternative relationality with/in the world and mathematics. She presents three Indigenous concepts that have been important to her while growing up—*In Lak’ech*, *reciprocity*, and *Nepantla*—and combines them to suggest *mathematx*. *In Lak’ech* refers to the notion in Mayan philosophy that we are all related—human and other-than-human—and that, thus, acting in alignment with the earth is acting in alignment with one’s own wellbeing.¹⁵ *Reciprocity* highlights that since different beings—both human and other-than-human—have different strengths and needs, we are all responsible in maintaining harmony of the cosmos as all beings must rely on others for what they lack.¹⁶ The third concept, *Nepantla*, “serves as a space of tensions, of multiple realities” (p. 13) and, thus, offers a space to acknowledge continuities and in-betweens where contradicting realities can coexist, contrasting Aristotelian logic. Through the notion of *Nepantla*, specifically, drawing emerges as a site of multiple realities coexisting and transforming each other, on which I elaborate in further detail in following sections. *Mathematx*, thus, offers a loving axio-onto-epistemology of mathematics that resonates with various notions of *agential realism* and that, hence, allows for a kind approach to drawing with/in mathematics and mathematics education

¹⁵ *In Lak’ech* means “you are the other me.” As Gutiérrez (2017) writes, “Seeing a version of oneself in other living beings or persons is a powerful reminder to move through the world with compassion, gratitude, and interdependence” (p. 7) because, as Bell (2013) writes through Anishinaabe philosophies, “what we do to the earth, we do to ourselves” (p. 105).

¹⁶ In order to maintain harmony in the world, it is necessary for one to be balanced: “If a person is whole and balanced, then he or she is in a position to fulfill his or her individual responsibilities to the whole” (Little Bear, 2000, p. 79). Thus, maintaining balance is not just a personal matter. Rather, it is an ethical stance in which one understands that *one’s wholistic wellbeing is crucial in being able to reciprocate harmoniously with/in the world*. Balance is not understood, however, as a fixed goal that once reached is permanent. Rather, balance is in constant flux and requires ongoing work.

research. I argue, in particular, that through *mathematx*, drawing emerges as a possible way to live *mathematx* and to (re)connect (to) continuities that one might have learned to fracture through harmful practices with/in mathematics and mathematics education research.

In particular, Gutiérrez suggests *mathematx* as “a radical reimagination of mathematics, a version that embraces the body, emotions, and harmony” (p. 15). She describes *mathematx* as “a way of seeking, acknowledging, and creating patterns for the purpose of solving problems (e.g., survival) and experiencing joy” (p. 15). Similar to Sinclair (2009) who argues for aesthetics as a liberating force in mathematics education, Gutiérrez draws from Dewey (1934) to point out the role that aesthetics play in meaning making and how “aesthetics join with emotion, pleasure, and understanding for humans as they relate to their world” (Gutiérrez, 2017, p. 16). Thus, she emphasizes that “*mathematx* is intricately tied to what is pleasing and rewarding *in a connected way*, not just a utilitarian or ‘problem solving’ manner” (p. 16, emphasis added). Thus, *mathematx* does not only involve patterns for survival but is also a way of expressing one’s sense of beauty and of connecting with others—human and other-than-human. *Mathematx* lives *in relation*. In resonance to the understanding through various Indigenous epistemologies of knowledge as dynamically living *in relations*—as knowing in becoming with/in agential realism—, *mathematx* emerges as a verb, as a mode of engagement with/in the world that is expressed with one’s whole ever-changing body, lived by all living beings, human and other-than-human, and that is inseparable from aesthetics and ethics since *mathematx* entails engaging with/in the world through In Lack’ech, reciprocity, and Nepantla as guiding principles in one’s becoming (with) mathematics.

Through the understanding of *mathematx* as a performance of joy and connection, as an expression of patterns “tied to what is pleasing and rewarding” while being guided by interconnectedness, reciprocity, and respect for multiple realities, then, I sense drawing as a possible way in which to live *mathematx*. More specifically, I experience drawing as a performance of joy and connection, as a way through which I express, relate with/in, and understand the world through patterns. Gutiérrez leaves what she means by *patterns* open. Through this openness, I do not understand patterns as only ones that are conventionally associated with ‘mathematics’—e.g., emerging sequences, functions, proofs, algorithms, diagrams, theorems, Aristotelian logic. Rather, I have come to understand patterns with/in *mathematx* as material, bodily, emotional, sensorial, dynamic (re)organizations—in all their expressive forms—of oneself as inseparable from the world, as one works for balance in order to be able to reciprocate, as one stays within tensions as an act of love and kindness, as one works towards reconciliation with/in oneself, with/in our fractured world. This understanding emerges for me through how Gutiérrez (2017) understands Las Tres Hermanas’ (corn, beans, and squash’s) reciprocal relationship—through Kimmerer’s (2013) description—as living *mathematx*:

Their layered spacing uses the light, a gift from the sun, efficiently, with no waste. The organic symmetry of forms belongs together; the placement of every leaf, the harmony of shapes speak their message. Respect one another, support one another, bring your gift to the world and receive the gift of others, and there will be enough for all. (p. 132)

Through figuring each other out reciprocally and respectfully, through (re)shaping themselves spatially and materially to “support one another,” to work towards balance, Las Tres Hermanas live *mathematx*. In resonance, when I refer to drawing with/in *mathematx*, I do not only refer to what is often perceived as ‘mathematical drawings,’ but also to *the act of drawing itself as a loving and material practice*—whether within a context that emerges as explicitly mathematical or not—as different bodies figure each other out while they transform and are transformed by each other, as they work towards balance. As Gutiérrez writes, “Living *mathematx* means both that we live a version of *mathematx* as well as *we are a living version of mathematx?*” (p. 14, emphasis added). In

resonance, I perceive the act of drawing as a way through which I am a living version of mathematx and, thus, as a way of expressing and connecting through patterns not only visually, but also bodily, emotionally, sensorially, relationally, spatially, materially—understanding patterns as emergent through different materialities, senses, rhythms, temporalities, spaces, logics, feelings/thoughts, bodies while drawing—and not just through the page.

Through the openness presented by Gutiérrez, I have allowed myself to understand patterns and mathematics as I *live/sense* them rather than continuing to fracture my feelings/thoughts/senses/experiences through colonizing forces that insist on a single form of mathematics—a dominant/dominating mathematics—as the only possible one. Accordingly, the drawings that I share throughout this paper, although they might not align with what is predominantly considered ‘mathematical drawings,’ are for me a way in which I live mathematx—through working out the composition of an emerging drawing with/in the world; through the joy of playing with/in the space of a page, with/in the feelings and knowledges that emerge cyclically/chaotically/rhythmically through all present beings; through the ways in which sometimes a drawing organizes itself to express new notions and possibilities; through the ways words are awakened by or awaken new possibilities and rhythms with/in a drawing; through the ways in which different matter participate, move, fit, shape, and guide each other; through what the movement of my eyes, my hands, my heart (to which I am not always attentive), and my mind (which often does not know how to let go) teaches me as we draw. That is, for me, drawing does *not* emerge as an ‘intermediary step’ towards some new axio-onto-epistemology of mathematics. Rather, for me, drawing through these understandings *is* mathematx—*is a* possible axio-onto-epistemology of mathematics—and so are myriad other expressivities and ways of becoming/feeling. Through mathematx, knowledge, lived experience, and ethical responsibility/accountability—epistemology, ontology, and axiology—are inseparable. It is this inseparability which I *feel* with/in my body as I draw. For this same reason, it has been the hardest thought/feeling/sensing to express through this paper, both because it cannot be reduced into language, particularly not the dominant one through which I am currently writing, and because I have learned to be afraid to share ideas if they diverge from hegemonic understandings of mathematics—especially if they are *felt*.

Through the openness of mathematx and its understanding of mathematics as *alive*, however, I have reconnected and conversed with my mathematics through poetry and have come to understand mathematics not just as verb but as *feeling*, both in the sense that it feels and that it *is a* feeling—an intensity. It is feeling “in a certain kind of way” (Benítez-Rojo, 1997, p. 10), feeling (at) home with/in the world—“That feeling / of the world and I shaping each other / to fit / with/in each other / to figure each other / out” (Abreu, 2022), reciprocally. This conversation, thus, foregrounded how intimate the relationship between my body and my understanding of mathematics/drawing is—what mathematics and drawing wake up in me is not the same that wakes up in others—, while at the same time how it has been inseparably shaped by historical and political forces as well. Accordingly, I want to emphasize that my intention is neither to offer my understandings of drawing and mathematics as the *only* possible ones nor present drawing as *the only* way to live mathematx. Rather, as mathematx recognizes that each person has their own ever-changing ways of connecting with/in the world and in resonance to how Gutiérrez describes mathematx—“The x at the end of the word signifies movement, an openness” (p. 14)—, I perceive the understandings with/in this paper as open and in continuous transformation, *drawing with/in mathematx* as a localized material articulation of a certain kind of feeling, dynamic, and ever-changing. Accordingly, my intention is rather to share drawing through these understandings as *a possible way* to live mathematx that is close to me, from my heart to others’, in the hopes that it

resonates or (re)invigorates each person's unique ways of expressing and connecting with others, human and other-than-human, through In Lak'ech, reciprocity, Nepantla, and their own felt and lived patterns/cycles.

Contrastingly to territorializing understandings of mathematics then, mathematx emerges as an axio-onto-epistemology, as inseparable from lived experience as well as from ethical responsibilities and, thus, is experienced, understood, felt, and related to in myriad intimate ways through different histories, materialities, and relations—there is a plurality of mathematics. Through sharing how drawing and mathematx converge with/in me, then, I hope to foreground the contingent, plural, interconnected, personal, multiple, dynamic, and transforming emergence of understanding and relationality with/in knowledge and the world, and thus, with/in what emerges as/with mathematics.

Drawing with/in Mathematx as a Dynamic and Indeterminate Practice through Indigenous Wisdoms-Agential Realism—Reverberations and Possibilities

It is important to note that when speaking of Indigenous Knowledges, *Indigenous* refers to Native nations and communities across the world. The term is not meant to imply that all Indigenous communities are the same, but that they share commonalities. Linda Tuhiwai Te Rina Smith (1999) points out that “Indigenous peoples’ is a relatively recent term which emerged in the 1970s out of the struggles primarily of the American Indian Movement (AIM), and the Canadian Indian Brotherhood. It is a term that internationalizes the experiences, the issues and the struggles of some of the world’s colonized peoples” (p. 7). However, it is important to clarify that there is no universal ‘Indigenous worldview.’ As Gutiérrez (2017) writes, “The use of particular languages and ties to particular lands create unique views held by Aboriginal peoples throughout the world and by individuals within those groups” (p. 6). Thus, the theoretical understandings presented here are not meant to be a universal Indigenous perspective at all since Indigenous Knowledges are tied to place. Rather, these theoretical understandings emerge as philosophical reverberations and from my own relationship with different Indigenous authors’ understandings of Indigenous Knowledges (e.g., Bell, 2013; Cajete, 2012; Cannella & Manuelito, 2008; Doolittle & Glanfield, 2007; Gutiérrez, 2017; Kimmerer, 2013; Little Bear, 2000; Million, 2015; TallBear, 2019; Tuck & Yang, 2014).

Through this relationship, the act of drawing emerges as a practice in which human and other-than-human beings are equally and inseparably active participants in the drawing encounter—as everything is imbued with spirit and in continuous motion—and from which knowledge emerges relationally and inseparably from its place of emergence. In resonance, although through different histories and materialities as well as ways of relating with/in and understanding the world, through agential realism, drawing emerges as a dynamic, indeterminate, and material practice where bodily boundaries are in constant flux—stabilizing and destabilizing—creating ever-changing pencil-human-mathematics-art-politics-paper-emotions-discourses-other-than-human amalgamations where matter and knowledge are inseparably active participants in the localized phenomenon of drawing, which has no pre-established end (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013; Ingold, 2013). In the following sections, I elaborate on these understandings through the diffraction of Indigenous Knowledges—based on Gutiérrez and other Indigenous scholars—and agential realism to perceive drawing as a practice with/in which: (1) matter/other-than-human persons are active participants, *including knowledge/ knowing* which is material, agential, and lives *in relations*; (2) all entities are interconnected/inseparable as we are all in flux with/in the world—we are all the world becoming itself; and (3) one can (re)attune/(re)sensitize oneself to the indeterminacy/dynamism and non-linearity of the world’s becoming; as well as (4) to perceive drawing as Nepantla, as a loving site of healing, multiple realities, and as an in-between the actualized and the possible.

Everything is Living with/in Drawing—Other-than-Human Participants. While through a representationalist approach a pencil and a piece of paper would be perceived as exclusively mediating tools to the agency of the human, and knowledge as a product of the human mind, through various Indigenous philosophies and agential realism, they are all in fact agentic, actively participating in the act of drawing as well. More specifically, *drawing can be understood/perceived as a dense node of human and other-than-human agencies—including knowledge/ knowing—encountering each other and actively bringing the world to matter.* In particular, through Indigenous philosophies, all entities—humans, plants, animals, rocks, water, matter, all other-than-human persons—are living beings, imbued with spirit (Gutiérrez, 2017; Little Bear, 2000; Martin 2017): “In Aboriginal philosophy, existence consists of energy. All things are animate, imbued with spirit, and in constant motion... There is no animate/inanimate dichotomy. Everything is more or less animate” (Little Bear, 2000, pp. 77–78). In resonance, Barad (2003) makes a different assumption from an anthropocentric view of the world through agential realism and recognizes the dynamism and agency of matter: “The inanimate is always being shoved to the side, as if it is too far removed from the human to matter, but that which we call inanimate is still very much bodily and lively” (Barad, 2012 as cited in de Freitas, 2017b, p. 743). Indigenous philosophies and agential realism, each with their own rhythms and relationalities, thus, emerge as possible ways to (re)attune to the liveliness and vibrancy of matter—which do not require humans to come to life—as well as their agency in the materialization of a drawing: e.g., the paper guides the pencil in a certain way through its texture, while the changing shape of the pencil’s lead allows for certain lines and not others, or the lead can suddenly break and leave an expressive mark. Accordingly, not only would paper, pencil, human be agentic but also all matter engaged in the encounter—a half-empty coffee mug from a tiny library in Coyoacán, an almost-too-full table that wobbles, a spider building their home in the corner of the room, a tree getting ready for the winter outside the window, an un/comfortable chair, dust through sunlight, barking dogs....

Because everything is living with/in a drawing encounter, then, through Indigenous philosophies, emerging knowledge lives *in* relations; it is not owned nor produced by a singular entity but is rather a localized ‘life force’—shared and transformed through all the relations in a place, never static: “If everything is animate, then everything has spirit and knowledge. If everything has spirit and knowledge, then all are like me. If all are like me, then all are my relations” (Little Bear, 2000, p. 78). Million (2015) emphasizes, thus, that knowledge is *embedded* in place and all its relations: “[I]t is the ‘land,’ not the speakers who are central. It is ‘all their relations’ in that place with the myriad entities that ‘make’ it [epistemology]. It [Epistemology] is the ‘life force’ as it is known in that ‘place’” (p. 342). Through this understanding together with mathematx, then, mathematics lives *in* relations and, thus, emerges and is experienced through multiple expressivities, relationalities, and living beings. In resonance, the mathematics that dynamically emerge as I draw with/in the world—as I live/become mathematx through drawing—live in the relations that are in motion through a drawing encounter. Thus, as I draw, I *feel* mathematics in different ways and through different relations, flows, materialities, rhythms, and (re)organizations inseparably with/in a page, with/in my body, with/in relations of a localized encounter. That is, I understand drawing as a site of knowing that is plural and agentic, where knowing can be poetic, mathematical, political, personal, physical, material, relational, historical, spatial, sensorial, spiritual, bodily, affective, expressive—all at the same time as these ways of knowing are inseparable with/in my becoming with/in the world, all carving into each other.

In resonance with Indigenous philosophies but through different language and energies, through agential realism mathematical knowledge and discourses emerge as agentic, material, and inseparable from the phenomenon where they emerged (Barad, 2003; de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013).

More specifically, with/in contexts that emerge more explicitly as ‘mathematical’—e.g., a ‘mathematics’ classroom—Sinclair, de Freitas, and Mikulan have offered different understandings and relationalities with/in mathematics through agential realism and other philosophies (e.g., Châtelet, 1993/2000; Deleuze, 1995; Massumi, 2011; Serres, 2011; Souriau, 1943/2015) by foregrounding the animacy and indeterminacy of mathematical concepts as well as their material existence and inseparability from a learner’s body (de Freitas, 2016; de Freitas & Sinclair, 2012, 2013; Mikulan & Sinclair, 2017, 2019). In particular, as de Freitas (2017b) writes, “concepts are not immaterial, detached codes for sorting and naming activity, nor are they mere distorted reflections of the world” (p. 741). Rather, concepts are material and active agents in the world’s materialization—not labels chosen by a subject to impose on inert matter. Accordingly, mathematical concepts are neither a construct nor a product of the human mind since all emerging concepts are the world wording itself. Mathematical concepts, thus, are not abstract static endpoints waiting to be arrived at or mentally constructed, nor is drawing a mediating tool towards such knowledge. Rather, mathematical concepts are very much material and alive—they are dynamic forces actively participating in the materialization of a drawing encounter. This understanding resonates with the notion of mathematics as alive within mathematx—as mathematics needing help from others to continue living while being able to reciprocate.

Perceiving matter and knowledge as lively and imbued with spirit offers a different understanding of the participants actively engaging in the act of drawing and (re)opens a different relationality with/in our material world—How might one act and relate differently with/in the world knowing that everything is living? Through Anishinaabe philosophies, for example, everything being alive implies that “knowledge/knowing without acknowledgement of the spiritual core, the moral code, is a very dangerous thing” (Forbes, 1998 as cited in Bell, 2013, p. 97). In resonance, through the understanding of everything as living and knowing, I have related to drawing more patiently and forgivingly, which has transformed my drawing practice. I have been able to allow myself to be guided by my pencil, paper, drawing hand, senses, emotions, knowledges, spiritual flows and forces, rather than trying to impose a static notion of what drawing and mathematics with/in drawing ‘should’ entail based on what my mind had learned. Indigenous philosophies have been guiding forces in allowing myself to reconnect to drawing as a way of knowing and becoming, a way that I have felt close to me since I was a kid but which I had learned to devalue. In particular, the understanding of knowledge as not just intellectual but also *felt*—“feelings are theory” (Million, 2009, p. 61)—has been transformational as I work towards healing my ways of knowing and becoming with/in the world. Being able to reciprocate to and live responsibly with/in our living world requires ongoing physical, emotional, mental, and spiritual work (Bell, 2013; Cajete, 2012; Doolittle & Glanfield, 2007; Gutiérrez, 2017; Little Bear, 2000).

Bodily Boundaries Queered with/in Drawing. While representationalism relies on the assumption that the world is comprised of discrete, separable entities that pre-exist relations—e.g., a pencil or pen might be perceived as a clearly delineated and discrete object with pre-determined boundaries and properties that are independent from a drawing encounter—, through Indigenous philosophies and agential realism, all agencies engaged in the encounter—pencils, pens, paper, tablet, humans, mathematical concepts, discourses, other-than-human entities, emotions—permeate and saturate each other, none with predetermined boundaries nor existent outside of the encounter.

In particular, while under a representationalist view a relation would involve separate preexisting entities with intrinsic characteristics—e.g., a paper, a pen, a human body, a table as discretely distinct—, through agential realism, “there are no independent relata, only relata-within-relations” (Barad, 2003, p. 815). Accordingly, Barad argues that all active agents, rather than

interacting, are *intra-acting*. More specifically, while interaction relies on the assumption of two *separate* entities relating with each other (see Figure 2), intra-action implies that these entities do not exist without each other and are thus inseparable (see Figure 3). That is, no entity is ontologically prior to—does not pre-exist—any other as the mattering of ‘one’ is entangled with the mattering of the ‘other’; ‘one’ does not exist without the ‘other.’ As Palmer (2011) writes, we cannot “separate what we are from the world around us” (p.15) since without that world, we are not this specific subject—and without us, that world is not that specific world. We are all the world becoming itself.

Figure 2. “Interaction.” Comic panels inspired by Minh-ha (1988) and Barad (2003). From *In-Betweens [comic]*, by S. Abreu, 2020, p. 23.

Figure 3. “Play of in/determinacy: intra-activity.” Within the panel, top caption reads, “... ‘while unsettling every definition of otherness arrived at’ [Minh-ha, 1988, para. 12]... ‘This play of in/determinacy unsettles the self/ other binary, difference is made and remade’ [Barad, 2014, p. 176].” Bottom caption reads, “Difference is not the opposite of sameness.” From *In-Betweens [comic]*, by S. Abreu, 2020, p. 28.

Barad uses the term *phenomena*, taken from Bohr, to refer to “*the ontological inseparability of agentially intra-acting ‘components’*” (p. 815, emphasis in original) and argues that phenomena “are ontologically primitive relations—relations without preexisting relata” (p. 815). Through agential realism, then, ‘entities’ or ‘components’ do not have an inherent nature or boundary. Rather, boundaries emerge *within* phenomena (see Figure 4): “It is through specific agential intra-actions that the boundaries and properties of the ‘components’ of phenomena become determinate and that particular embodied concepts become meaningful” (p. 815). That is, boundaries are not intrinsic properties of bodies—they do not sit still—but are rather continuously emerging within phenomena through intra-activity: the boundaries between a paper, a pencil, a human body, a table are no longer clearly delineated since they continuously shift as they emerge and fuse with/in different amalgamations. Thus, since through agential realism boundaries of bodies are not predetermined but rather continuously (re)configured, the body is understood as indeterminate boundary-shifting amalgamations of human and more-than-human, rather than a predetermined entity whose boundary is a clear separation between inside and outside the body (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013). Thus, drawings are no longer perceived as externalizations of pre-existing ideas in the human mind, materializations of otherwise immaterial concepts, nor as an activity in which separate pre-determined entities interact with each other. Rather, *drawing becomes a dynamic and material practice where bodily boundaries are in constant flux, stabilizing and destabilizing—creating ever-changing pencil-human-mathematics-art-paper-emotions-knowledges-histories-discourses-other-than-human amalgamations as entities materialize each other through entanglements and agential differentiatings, continuously transforming each other*. As de Freitas and Sinclair (2012) write, drawing emerges as “a highly material process of becoming entwined and enfolded with the material surfaces engaged in the encounter” (p. 151). All bodies—human, matter, knowledge—continuously and materially transform and are transformed in the phenomenon:

The diagram is...a mechanism for carving up space while embedded in space. It is not a representation nor even a metaphor that operates along an oblique line of referral (although there are indeed mathematical entities that function that way), but rather a device that grasps (traps and contracts) the material world. (p. 139–140)

Accordingly, mathematical concepts and knowledges are continuously materialized and (re)configured as well and, so, do not exist ontologically separate from what is known: “Conceptual content is not a representation of an object, but a *material* articulation of a phenomenon, which encompasses both meaning and what is meant” (Rouse, 2016, as cited in de Freitas, 2017, p. 746, emphasis added). Thus, Barad’s agential realism is an onto-epistemology. That is, there is no break between epistemology and ontology as they are entangled, materializing each other—one cannot exist without the other since there is no ontological, material, separation between them. It is knowing *in* becoming—which resonates with knowledge/knowing living in relations through Indigenous philosophies.

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Figure 4. “Phenomena—we are the world materializing itself.” Citation is from Barad (2014, p. 174) from which the illustration was inspired as well. From *In-Betweens [comic]*, by S. Abreu, 2020, p. 29.

Because through agential realism boundaries are the effect of dynamic agential differences and there are no entities ontologically prior to any other, then, there are no predetermined properties of matter. Thus, boundaries and properties are continuously (re)configured and (re)articulated. That is, boundaries are stabilized and destabilized *within* specific intra-actions, and, hence, they are contingent borders rather than absolute. Thus, the world *is* agential dynamism and is *indeterminate*:

The ongoing flow of agency through which “part” of the world makes itself differentially intelligible to another “part” of the world and through which local causal structures, boundaries, and properties are stabilized and destabilized does not take place in space and time but in the making of spacetime itself. *The world is an ongoing open process of mattering through which ‘mattering’ itself acquires meaning and form in the realization of different agential possibilities... Relations of exteriority, connectivity, and exclusion are reconfigured. The changing topologies of the world entail an ongoing reworking of the very nature of dynamics.* (Barad, 2003, p. 817, emphasis added)

Thus, the mattering of the universe, including the materialization of meaning, is ever-changing, entangled, and dynamic (see Figure 5): “[M]eaning is not ideational but rather specific material (re)configurings of the world, and semantic indeterminacy, like ontological indeterminacy, is only locally resolvable through specific intra-actions” (Barad, 2003, p. 819). It is important to note, thus, that indeterminacy through agential realism is not about relativism—i.e., it is not an epistemological matter. Rather, “indeterminacy is intrinsic to matter and not simply a reflection of our limited skills at observation and measurement” (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013, p. 460).

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Figure 5. “Boundaries and relations continuously reconfiguring.” Panels inspired by and quoting Barad (2003, p. 818). From *In-Betweens [comic]*, by S. Abreu, 2020, p. 25.

Through agential realism, then, drawing with/in mathematics can be understood as a continuous (re)organizing of matter—where matter is mathematical concepts, knowledges, drawing instruments and surfaces, other-than-human entities, humans, emotions, and myriad other agencies blending into each other. *Knowing in drawing is a localized ongoing material (re)configuring of boundaries and potentialities where knowledges, including mathematical concepts, are not determinate immaterial ideas but active and indeterminate agencies locally materializing.*

Through agential realism, then, drawing is not an act of representing something that exists independently in the mind or in some abstract/ideal world. Rather, it is a material phenomenon within which emerging drawings and knowledges are co-constitutive, inseparable—it is knowing in drawing in becoming as bodily boundaries are in continuous transformation as all agencies intra-act and “carve” each other. A drawing is thus never ‘finished’ as it continues to have its own agency, materially transforming, and being transformed by, the world (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2012). Hence, it is not frozen ‘evidence’ of a person’s thought but is an active force that continues living and changing with/in the world (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. “Drawing not as ‘evidence’ but as an active force.” Drawings that became with me as I studied for my Algebra qualifying exams in 2020. These drawings, however, are neither ‘evidence’ of some mental structures that live in my mind nor materializations of otherwise immaterial concepts. Rather, they are active forces, transforming and being transformed by the world, bringing ever-changing knowledge to matter, in their own ways as they intra-act with/in the world.

It is important to note that entanglements are not unities; they do not imply agential homogeneity. Rather, entanglements entail agential differences, and boundaries are the *effect* of agential differences encountering each other: “The world *is* intra-activity in its differential mattering. It is through specific intra-actions that a differential sense of being is enacted in the ongoing ebb and flow of agency” (Barad, 2003, p. 817, emphasis in original). I perceive this notion like waves in the sea: all inseparable but saturating the sea with different ever-changing energies, rhythms, and agencies that co-constitute each other, becoming differentiated through their relationality with ‘each other’ while being continuously transformed by and transforming others, all at the same time—e.g., boundaries that did not exist before emerge as waves crash into each

other which then become multiple and (re)configure new boundaries, or emerging tensions from waves pulling on each other configure different agential flows which simultaneously (re)configure the dynamics of these same emerging tensions, or different waves might find rhythmic resonances with each other and become one until they are perturbed by sudden tides which (re)configure them once more, never the same as they were before, never existing in isolation nor pre-determined, always saturating the sea with different agential flows. This notion reverberates with the understanding of everything with/in the world being interconnected and in continuous flux through Indigenous Knowledges, on which I elaborate in following sections.

Thus, for example, while drawing, a hand-pen-sitting-body amalgamation can be perceived as a dynamic wave crashing into paper waves, all of them continuously becoming one, parting ways, reuniting once more, while ink-waves find their own flow, saturating paper-skin-emotions-concepts waves, while being magnetically guided at the same time by paper-texture waves and by feelings-theories-politics-mathematics waves which rise and fall as they swell and are chopped by unexpected agential tides, like a calming sleeping-cat wave that smooths the currents or an academic-institutional-pressure storm that overpowers any dissenting flow, while a hard-surface-desk wave supports the weight of multiple flows and as hot-coffee-infusing-mouth-and-heart waves reinvigorate, or at times soothe, bodily waves as they transform and are transformed by this lively sea of myriad other agencies—all different forces with dynamic potencies but inseparable in their mutual becoming. In the words of Barad (2014), entanglements “do not erase differences; on the contrary, entanglings entail differentiating, differentiating entails entanglings. One move—cutting *together-apart*” (p. 176, emphasis in original). Through agential realism, then, drawing is a phenomenon of waves encountering each other, intra-acting, transforming, and materializing each other—where drawings and emerging knowledges are co-constitutive waves rather than ontologically separate.

This understanding of knowing as inseparable from a phenomenon resonates with the Indigenous notion that knowledge/knowing lives in relations—is inseparable from place. Accordingly, both agential realism and Indigenous wisdoms have reattuned me to the contingency of what emerges as *mathematics*. More specifically, through reconnecting with the closeness that I felt between drawing and mathematics, it was foregrounded for me how highly contingent and deeply intimate this understanding is. Thus, I have come to understand my perception of and relationality with/in *drawing as living mathematx* as a possible manifestation *out of a plurality of possible loving mathematics* since the emergence of this understanding—of drawing as *mathematx*—is inseparably tied to and lives through the different forces that converge with/in my becoming. Accordingly, the understanding of knowledge/knowing living in relations and being inseparable from one’s becoming *entails* an ever-changing plurality of mathematics since the agential cuts that bound what emerges as *mathematics* are contingent to localized, indeterminate, and dynamic nodes of existence. That is, there is no force or matter that is intrinsically ‘*mathematics*.’ Rather, *mathematics* continuously emerges in/through/as different ways, forms, relations, materialities, and understandings—or might not even emerge at all—since what emerges as *mathematics* is contingent on the agencies and (historical, political, affective, aesthetic, social, emotional) material forces with/in a phenomenon.

I also argue that through the particular bodily engagement entailed in the act of drawing, the transformative potential of knowledge can be felt not only ‘intellectually’ but throughout the body. That is, through (re)attuning to the materiality of the body, the agency of knowledge, and their inseparability while drawing, one can (re)open one’s senses to the body’s ways of knowing, being, and relating with/in the body and with/in the world. For example, for me, drawing often emerges as a manual (and visual) practice. Throughout my various experiences with drawing, a lot of my

frustrations used to emerge from my hands ‘not doing what I wanted them to,’ from feeling that my mind did not have sufficient control over my drawing movements. My traces were often contrived and overworked. Through gradually engaging with my drawing practices through new understandings, however, I have learned to trust my hand as knowledgeable, as knowing participant, and given her the space and freedom to do and express what she knows instead of trying to control her through my mind’s ways of knowing. Reconnecting with my hands in this way has in turn made me realize that I have often silenced or ignored my body, leaving her out of my understandings of ‘knowledge’ and of my ways of getting to know (with) the world. Thus, I am continuously trying to be more attentive to how I have fractured and hurt my body and to be respectful of my body’s ways of knowing, being, and relating with/in the world. Through my own lived experience, then, I sense that these understandings can help one re-spect—“to look again” (Bell, 2013, p. 97) at—one’s body as knowledgeable, as knowing. How might one relate with one’s body differently if one respects it as knowledgeable? As knowing? Might one understand oneself differently, not as fractured into mind and body but as a fluctuating *mindbody*? What ways of knowing might one (re)connect with that might not take the form of, or rely on, ‘mental,’ ‘conscious,’ or ‘intentional’ awareness (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2012)? What might one’s body know that one has learned to silence? Which expressivities might (re)open when one trusts one’s body as knowing matter?

Through these understandings then, one can be (re)sensitized while drawing to not only how knowledge and matter might be a/effecting one’s traces, shapes, use of space on a drawing surface, the materials one engages with, how one engages with them, how they engage with one, but also one’s feelings/thoughts/senses/sensibilities/moods/expressivities, how knowledge and matter might be transforming the body differentially as they relate differently with one’s hands, eyes, back, restless feet, and how all of this in turn continuously and materially transforms one’s and the world’s becoming. More specifically, then, while drawing one can (re)attune to different agential energies and knowledges emerging through, and transforming, one’s own body as different energies, that emerge as different parts of the body, intra-act differently with the material world as one draws—e.g., when drawing emerges as a manual practice, “your hand can do things your eyes know little about” (Nathalie Sinclair, April 29, 2022, personal communication).

These understandings make me wonder, how might one’s body with/in the world be living mathematically in ways that cannot be subsumed into words or some ‘conscious’ way of knowing but which are still very much active in the becoming of a drawing (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2012)? How might (re)connecting with one’s body as an ever-changing knowing flow transform one’s drawing practices? What might the hands draw when the eyes are closed? What might other parts of one’s body—the feet, the mouth, the arms, the legs—express and relate to through drawing? How might drawing emerge when one is (re)sensitized to the expressivities and liveliness of other-than-human beings as well, including matter not conventionally associated with drawing?

Drawing as Dynamic and In/determinate—as ‘Dynamic but without Motion’. Because the materialization of the world is indeterminate, Barad uses the term *virtual* from quantum field theory to refer to what de Freitas (2017b) describes as “the plane of trans-touching conceptual dynamism by which a concept is actualized” (p. 744). In particular, when a mathematical concept emerges within a phenomenon, i.e., is actualized—for example, when the concept of a circle or a cube emerges while children are playing with different materials—, this concept is still tied to the virtual plane of all the infinite concepts that could have been (de Freitas, 2017b). Mikulan and Sinclair (2017) discuss the term virtual in new materialisms as well, but through Deleuze’s (1995) philosophy: “The virtual is a key term, coming from Deleuze...that enabled him to describe multiplicities that are real but that are never fully formed, determined or exhausted, and thus never

actualized” (p. 6). They argue that matter is indeterminate—it does not follow predetermined patterns—, but rather it is constantly (re)organizing and (re)configuring itself; it expresses multiplicity:

Unlike an essence, a multiplicity is not uniform and timeless, but divergent and alters historically. “*To say that an object expresses a multiplicity, is to say that matter is spontaneously capable of generating pattern, and that such pattern does not resemble some pre-given form*” [de Freitas & Sinclair, 2017] (Mikulan & Sinclair, 2017, p. 6, emphasis added)

Perceiving matter as spontaneously generating patterns, I argue, is a way through which to appreciate matter as living mathematx, as expressing their sense of beauty and connection with/in the world through patterns. Thus, the convergence of mathematx and the notion of multiplicity with/in me resensitized me to matter’s expressivities and modes of engagement with/in the world through patterns. That is, it reattuned me to how other-than-human beings might be expressing their own sense of appreciation and reciprocity through patterns—how they are living mathematx—, which has in turn made me ask, how can I reciprocate? Moreover, it has helped me reconnect with mathematics as not an exclusively human nor mental activity. As Gutiérrez (2017) writes, “Living mathematx means moving through the world with other living beings, acknowledging, appreciating, and reciprocating the patterns produced” (p. 14). Moreover, the understanding of matter continuously (re)organizing itself and generating patterns without some pre-given form reconnected me to the feeling that I have had that making art—the act of drawing more specifically for me—is a way of *becoming/performing/playing* mathematics with other living beings, is a form of bodily mathematics which cannot be subsumed neither within symbols nor language. Thus, a ‘final’ artwork or drawing for me is not a representation of such mathematics. Rather, it has its own agency and can spontaneously generate patterns of its own with/in the world—*play* mathematics in its own ways through different relations with/in its world as it continues to (re)organize itself in relations.

Moreover, through the notion of multiplicities, drawing is reconnected to the vibrancy of the virtual, to the indeterminacy of spatial, temporal, and bodily boundaries. More specifically, as the virtual—what could be—and the actual—what is actualized—are co-existing and in superposition, *drawing can be sensed, then, as a continuity among tensions of the actualized and the potential, as a site of interacting potentialities where uncertainty is right at the tip of any drawing material—or rather, right in the vibrant liminal space pencil/paper*. In resonance, de Freitas and Sinclair (2013) sense a diagram as “an experiment at the threshold between the actual and the virtual” (de Freitas, 2016, p. 188) through Châtelet’s (1993/2000) understanding of diagrams. In particular, de Freitas (2016), guided by Massumi (2011), emphasizes the speculative nature of vision to highlight that a figure is “the result of a *habitual oversight, an entrained blocking* of the potentiality or virtuality (‘the imperceptible’) that is always entailed in perception” (p. 197, emphasis added). Viewing a drawing as a representation, then, can be understood as blinding oneself to—“blocking of”—the virtuality present in any phenomenon of drawing and limiting one’s viewing to the already-actualized. Through agential realism, however, drawing emerges as a dynamic, indeterminate, and material practice, rich of vibrant possibilities in superposition, even if not all perceived: “An object’s appearance is an event, full of all sorts of virtual movement. We live on ‘speculative investments’ as though we were surfing ‘the front edge of a wave-crest’ [Massumi, 2011]” (p. 194). More specifically, then, drawing emerges as a node of transformation and potential where the indeterminacy of the world can become more palpable as, as Ingold (2013) says, “All the time when you’re drawing, the line is moving on. ... That line is continuously at risk. Anything can happen” (14:54). Based on Klee’s (1961) understanding of drawing as “taking a line for a walk” (p. 105), he emphasizes the uncertainty and vulnerability entailed in such an act—just as one walks, one does not know what

is to transpire. By understanding drawing in this way, then, one can (re)attune to the “virtual movement,” to overlooked potentialities as one draws. In turn, this (re)attunement to indeterminacy can (re)open one’s body to other possible ways of knowing, relating, and becoming (with) the world. Moreover, through this understanding, drawings that are viewed or that emerge more explicitly as ‘mathematical drawings’ can be understood as a continuity, as an in-between among the tensions of (in)determinacy—in other words, as the coexistence of two equally important forces: the force of uncertainty and the force of desire for certainty that often emerges with/in mathematics as a discipline.

Moreover, de Freitas (2017b) argues that “quantum field theory shows how each ‘individual’ always already includes an infinitude of intra-actions with itself *through infinitude of virtual others*” (p. 744, emphasis in original), from which one, never pre-given nor pre-determined, will be actualized within a phenomenon—“[M]any potentialities exist in superposition (light is a wave and a particle), only one of which will be actualised at the moment of observation” (Mikulan & Sinclair, 2019, p. 240). Accordingly, while drawing, not only is indeterminism vibrant right at the tip of the pencil but also with/in one’s whole body as one’s “entire history...exists virtually; her affective, cognitive, aesthetic, social, political and gendered history” (Mikulan & Sinclair, 2019, p. 241), continuously transforming with/in the materialization of a drawing phenomenon. As Barad (2014) writes, “Each moment is an infinite multiplicity. ‘Now’ is not an infinitesimal slice but an infinitely rich condensed node in a changing field diffracted across spacetime in its ongoing iterative repatterning [see Figure 7]” (p. 169). *Drawing can be sensed, thus, as an “infinite multiplicity,” as an indeterminate, dense node iteratively repatterning, rich in potentialities with no pre-established endpoints, and where the actualized and the virtual are in a strong, palpable tension—through the threshold of a drawing surface, one’s body, the vibrancy of matter.* Agential realism, thus, offers an understanding of drawing that foregrounds potentialities and that (re)opens the senses to their intrinsic indeterminacy.

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Figure 7. “Now’ as a dense node of multiplicities; boundaries de/ stabilizing; knowing in being.” Ideas are drawn from Barad (2003, 2014). In retrospect, I wish I had illustrated the notion of destabilizing through a non-linear chaos instead of something that resembles a frenzy of thread. From *In-Betweens [comic]*, by S. Abreu, 2020, p. 30.

In resonance, through Indigenous understandings, everything in the cosmos is in constant motion, ever-changing, and interconnected—“Creation is a continuity”—, and, thus, there is no predetermined endpoint nor a hierarchical or evolutionary structure of time and space:

The idea of all things being in constant motion or flux leads to a holistic and cyclical view of the world. ... It results in a concept of time that is dynamic but without motion. Time is part of the constant flux but goes nowhere. Time just is. (Little Bear, 2000, p. 78)

Accordingly, various Indigenous and other scholars point towards the hegemonic understanding of time as progressively linear as an imposition in favor of colonizing interests (e.g., Boletsi et al., 2021; Million, 2015; TallBear, 2019; Visvanathan, 2005), and argue instead for a spatial, intimate relationality with/in the everyday—“In this realm of energy and spirit, interrelationships between all entities are of paramount importance, and space is a more important referent than time” (Little Bear, 2000, p. 77)—rather than a constant preoccupation for an elusive/ideal future that always exist somewhere other than the present (e.g., Liboiron et al., 2018; TallBear, 2019). In resonance, I argue that drawing emerges as a practice that (re)attunes one to one’s spatial interconnectedness with/in the world as well as to the flow of time going nowhere in particular, while at the same time, becomes a way to *express* this same spatial and non-linear relationality with/in the world through the queering of spatial and timely boundaries through the openness and all-at-once relationality of a drawing surface (see Figure 8). That is, through drawing one can express the contingency and dynamism of boundaries through the possibility of immersing into the composition of a drawing all-at-once and not necessarily in a linear manner—unlike language (Sousanis, 2015). Thus, even though one might not be able to disentangle completely from linear structures—nor might want to—, one can (re)attune to and express non-linear possibilities through the palpable spatial relationality of a drawing surface with/in drawing.

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Figure 8. “All beings interconnected, in constant flux, going nowhere in particular but always in motion.” Inspired by, and with citations from, *Little Bear* (2000, p.78) and *Kimmerer* (2013, p.114). From *Young Philosophers: What Can They Teach Us about the Concept of Space?* [comic], by H. Dominguez & S. Abreu, 2021, p. 8.

Moreover, through the tentativeness of a drawing—“the evocation of the possible in drawing” (Nathalie Sinclair, June 20, 2022, personal communication)—one can (re)attune to the sensing of time as going nowhere in particular since the possibilities that can be awakened through drawing are endlessly rhizomatic and indeterminate. Through the spatial relationality entailed in drawing, drawing allows for (re)organizations of and relationalities with/in matter that are different from the ones allowed through linear structures such as written text or colonizing notions of time. More specifically, drawing allows for expressivities that (re)sensitize one to all-at-once relationalities, to multiplicity and superpositions, as one engages with the spatial (re)configurations of drawing on a surface. Sousanis (2015), through his comic book *Unflattening*, argues for and presents possibilities, expressivities, and ways of knowing that are not constrained within linearity, specifically the linear cage of written and spoken language. As he writes, “The verbal marches along linearly, step by step, a discrete sequence of words ‘strung one after another,’ ..., ‘like beads on a rosary’ [Langer,

1957]. The visual on the other hand... presents itself all-at-once [.] simultaneous [.] all over relational” (p. 58). In resonance, I argue that the all-over relationality of a drawing surface has the potential to (re)connect one to non-linear, endlessly rhizomatic, possibilities and understandings, particularly when drawing is perceived through non-hierarchical, non-human centric, and relational philosophies that embrace indeterminacy—such as Indigenous Knowledges and agential realism. In this way, drawing can emerge as a way to (re)attune to multiplicities since “while comics are read sequentially like text, the entire composition [of the page] is also taken in—viewed—all-at-once... Comics hold sequential and simultaneous modes in electric tension” (pp. 62–63). Unlike verbal expressivities then, expressivities through drawing are not necessarily constrained to a linear engagement as there is no clearly delineated order to follow. Thus, they have the potential to (re)attune one to the in/determinacy of the encounter, to the superposition of possibilities, to the dynamism of perception (see Figure 9). That is, through this understanding, drawing is not about expressing particular futures. Rather, it is about *(re)awakening* one’s perceptions to the intrinsic indeterminacy of the world through the myriad, indeterminate possibilities that drawing evokes. In this way, drawing—similar to time—“is dynamic but without motion.”

Figure 9. “Drawing is dynamic but without motion; the in/determinacy of perception.” Multiple possibilities of how to ‘read’ each image exist simultaneously as there is no delineated order in which to engage with their composition. The in/determinacy of these readings has the potential to (re)attune oneself to the intrinsic in/determinacy and dynamism of perception and becoming. Left: Digital painting by S. Abreu, 2017. Right: Gouache painting by S. Abreu, 2020.

Drawing as Nepantla and as a Site of Healing. In this section, I suggest that drawing can also be understood as Nepantla, not only through its all-at-once composition on a drawing surface which allows for the coexistence of multiple realities, but also through the act of drawing itself. As discussed earlier, Nepantla is one of the three Indigenous concepts from which Gutiérrez (2017) draws to suggest mathematx. More specifically, Gutiérrez draws from Anzaldúa’s understanding of Nepantla as spaces of tensions, multiple realities, and interstitial spaces that can be generative

since they can be spaces for bridging differences without erasing them. As Anzaldúa and Keating (2002) write, “In Nepantla, you are exposed, open to other perspectives, more readily able to access knowledge derived from inner feelings, imaginal states, and outer events, and to ‘see through’ them with a mindful, holistic awareness” (as cited by Gutiérrez, 2017, p. 10). Through this “mindful, holistic awareness,” one can stay within tensions without falling into the (learned) impulse to erase difference. As Gutiérrez (2017) writes,

Bridging between two different views requires deep intellectual and emotional work. It means being willing to hold two or more contradictory views in one’s mind at the same time with the goal of not quickly coming to a conclusion that subsumes both ideas under an umbrella but maintains some of those views and reaches a third space that is neither and both of those views. The idea of Nepantla is consistent with Aboriginal knowledge of the metaphoric mind where we have the ability to hold two completely different thoughts simultaneously. (p. 11)

Moreover, similarly to the notion of intra-activity with/in phenomena through agential realism, one is not only *in* Nepantla; one *is* Nepantla: “That is, I am situated within a space of tensions and multiple realities that is called Nepantla. And, by virtue of being in that space, I am also the thing called Nepantla; I contribute to its essence” (Gutiérrez, 2017, p. 11). Anzaldúa highlights, however, that even if we are all related, we are also different. She signifies this sameness/otherness with the term *nos/otras* (Gutiérrez, 2012). The placing of the slash indicates that we are all connected—*nos*, we—while at the same time recognizing our differences—*otras*, others. This resonates with Barad’s understanding of the world coming to be by the move “cutting together-apart” as “entanglings entail differentiating, differentiating entail entanglings” (Barad, 2003, p. 176).

For me, drawing emerges as Nepantla in multiple ways. For example, perceiving drawing as the threshold between the actual and the virtual as discussed in the previous section can also be understood as a way in which drawing is Nepantla. In particular, drawing emerges as the liminal space between the actualized and the multiple possible realities that have not yet materialized, but which are very much present and vibrant, as a space open to possibilities different from and that do not resolve into the already-actualized—the actualized and the potential in high tension and vibrantly coexisting in a drawing node. Another way in which I understand drawing as Nepantla is through the all-at-once relationality of a drawing surface. By being able to perceive a drawing’s spatial composition all-at-once, multiple worlds can coexist simultaneously both with/in a drawing surface and the perceiving senses. Drawing thus becomes a space of multiple realities which is neither and all those realities at the same time and that can, thus, create something new through the tensions that emerge from the coexistence of manifold worlds. By allowing different realities to live with/in the same space simultaneously, drawing emerges as a space in which one can work towards bridging without subsuming—being a bridge to reach a third space, being Nepantla. At the same time, the act of drawing lives in its own Nepantla as one can argue that the act of drawing is in a sense linear—one’s traces can be perceived as linear—and, thus, lives in a liminal space between linearity and non-linear expressivities and relationalities through a drawing surface, neither exclusively one or the other, nor fully both (Nathalie Sinclair, June 20, 2022, personal communication). What might emerge from mindfully staying with/in the tensions of non/linearity while/through drawing?

Moreover, *the practice of drawing itself as a node of existence*, and not just a drawing surface, can be perceived as Nepantla since drawing can be understood as a generative encounter of multiple realities—of tensions amongst different ways of knowing and becoming—where one is in constant motion and transformation. Accordingly, the performance of drawing as Nepantla offers a generative and loving space in which to explore dynamism and in/determinacy—“Nepantla has

been compared to the action of walking, whereby one is constantly in motion and where each step shifts the center of gravity so there is no solid grounding” (Gutiérrez, 2017, p. 10). More specifically, the act of drawing as *Nepantla* emerges as a practice in which one is continuously transitioning, border-crossing, between multiple realities and materializations of oneself and the world inseparably—connecting with “knowledge derived from inner feelings, imaginal states, and outer events... [seeing through them] with a mindful, holistic awareness”—coexisting with different knowledges/emotions and seeming contradictions, being a *Nepantlerx* (see Figure 10). Gutiérrez argues that being a *Nepantlerx*, “one who chooses to live in a place of tensions—as a border crosser” (p. 10), is powerful. Deciding to stay within tensions long enough to birth new knowledge, instead of picking one side over the other, is a loving choice: “[T]o bridge is an act of will, an act of love, an attempt toward compassion and reconciliation, and a promise to be present with the pain of others without losing themselves [oneself] to it” (Anzaldúa & Keating, 2002, as cited by Gutiérrez, 2017, p. 11).

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Figure 10. “The act of drawing as *Nepantla*.” As I drew, I connected with “knowledge derived from inner feelings, imaginal states, and outer events” as I tried to embrace the uncertainty of the world while the pandemic reached a peak. Through these drawings, I lived feelings of both isolation and interconnectedness simultaneously—amongst many others—trying to not lose myself with/in the sadness of unexpected losses and a profound feeling of isolation. The act of drawing emerged as a third space for me to emerge with new *conocimientos*. Left: *Somos Mar* [comic] by S. Abreu, 2021. Published in *Pluvia*. (<https://www.revistapluvia.com/post/somos-mar>). Right: *Idas y vueltas* by S. Abreu, 2021. Published in *Pluvia*. (<https://www.revistapluvia.com/post/idas-y-vueltas>).

Acknowledging that one is able to hold two contradictory views simultaneously, that things can be both the same and different as signified by *nos/otras* (see Figure 11), moreover, (re)opens a relationality with/in knowing and becoming that does not rely on binary thinking—e.g., Aristotelian logic or discrete categorizations—nor on the need to subsume everything into a single understanding. As mentioned earlier, *Nepantla* has been a guiding force with/in my conversations with agential realism, mathematx, and Indigenous wisdoms together, reminding me not to reduce one into the other and to work towards generating a “third space.” Moreover, through *Nepantla*, drawing and mathematics emerge as multiple, as ever-changing modes of engagement that can

emerge in myriad ways and through dynamic understandings that are valuable in different ways and that are neither mutually exclusive, all-encompassing, containable, universal, final, nor superior to any other. Accordingly, drawing with/in mathematics can emerge as all the understandings presented in this paper—and manifold more!—simultaneously or not, and/or even just ephemerally—and, thus, not just as either a ‘process’ towards some defined endpoint or a finalized ‘product’ as is often understood through conventional theoretical approaches within mathematics education research.

Figure 11. Citations by Minh-ba (1988, para. 12) except for last panel which citations are as follow: “... ‘while unsettling every definition of otherness arrived at’ [Minh-ba, 1988, para. 12]... ‘This play of in/determinacy unsettles the self/ other binary, difference is made and remade’ [Barad, 2014, p. 176].” From *In-Betweens* [comic], by S. Abreu, 2020, pp. 27–28.

Through reconnecting lovingly with mathematics as a living entity and to the ways that my body—and not just my fractured mind—relates with, knows, and enjoys the world, moreover, I have gradually reattuned, in a way that resonates with my own ways of becoming, to my lifelong sensing of art and mathematics as inseparable and co-constitutive with/in my becoming. With/in this work of healing, Nepantla has offered me a different space from which to understand the inseparability that I sensed between art and mathematics—instead of having to fracture it as binary Western thinking had taught me to (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. “Multiplicity of art and mathematics.” From *Algebrita* [unpublished poem], by S. Abreu, 2022.

Moreover, acknowledging my interconnectedness while drawing and my responsibility to the world, with a desire to reciprocate, has transformed my drawing practice while at the same time, approaching my drawing practice lovingly has transformed the knowledges that become with/in me, the materialities that emerge. By approaching matter, ideas, feelings, sensations, thoughts, other-than-human participants lovingly while drawing—and wherever I become—, my mindbody continuously becomes (re)sensitized to possibilities that I had often ignored/shut down through judgement. Drawing has become a powerful way to express and live my subjectivities, connect with others, reopen my senses to the vibrancy and agency of all living beings as well as to the inseparability of my becoming from the world (see Figure 13), inhabit tensions long enough to emerge with new understandings, pay attention to cycles and patterns in search for balance and healing, take the time to be mindful of my practices and recognize which ones might be hurtful to others in order to try to change them, and often times simply to experience joy. Thus, for me, drawing and other expressivities have the potential to become places rich in generative forces through which to birth new knowledges and (re)configurings of matter—if one is perceptive to them.

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Figure 13. "Gifts of the four directions." Illustration (2021) that emerged as I engaged with Bell (2013) as I work towards reconnecting with other ways of knowing, becoming, and relating with/in the world.

(Re)opening Possibilities with/in Mathematics and Mathematics Education through Drawing

Even though mathematics has been approached through various art forms before (e.g., Dietiker, 2015; LaHaye & Naested, 2014), it has still been with the focus on implementing an already established mathematics curriculum rather than as an indeterminate and dynamic form of expression that brings joy. Through agential realism and Indigenous Knowledges, however, drawing, and each person's own expressivities, have the potential to become generative encounters rather than reifying ones. In particular, the alternative understanding of drawing that emerges through this paper can help mathematics educators (re)attune to the liveliness and in/determinacy of the world and, thus, to other possibilities, continuities, expressivities, and complexities that do not reinforce judgmental practices that are reified through representationalism in theoretical understandings of drawing with/in mathematics. Moreover, through mathematics as an axio-onto-epistemology of mathematics, one's responsibility in how one relates with/in knowledge is foregrounded and, thus, transforms how one, as an emerging researcher/teacher/learner, engages

with/in knowledge-creation practices. Through agential realism and Indigenous Knowledges, all dichotomies and breaks imposed by representationalist approaches—e.g., axiology/epistemology/ontology, knowledge/lived experience, mind/body, rational/emotional, abstract/material, objective/subjective, mathematics/art, inanimate/animate, inside/outside the body, human/environment—are queered, (re)opening not only our perceptions and bodies to continuities and complexities that have been fractured but also our ways of knowing and our relationality to knowledge to no longer be constrained within imposed disciplinary boundaries and reifying hurtful practices, but rather fluidly emerging and transforming with/in lived experiences and localized reverberations. Thus, practices of knowledge creation are (re)connected to affective and ethical elements and to expressions of connection, sense of beauty, reciprocity, and joy.

In resonance, by (re)sensitizing one to the fluidity and vibrant in/determinacy of spatial, temporal, and bodily boundaries—including not only through a drawing surface but through one's entire body through their histories, materialities, and multiplicities—, drawing emerges as a possible way to (re)attune to other expressivities of knowing in becoming as well as to loving potentialities of mathematical activity that are inseparable from becoming and from axiological matters through mathematx. It (re)connects one's body to their materiality, immediacy, and responsibility with/in the world while at the same time materializing and sensing new possibilities—the actual and the potential in intense tension. Drawing with/in mathematx through the guiding principles of In Lak'ech, reciprocity, and Nephantla, then, can help one (re)attune to a mathematics and a way of doing research that is in/determinate and open—to the body, to other-than-human doers, to interconnectedness, non-linear expressivities, tensions and contradictions, to difference, affective elements, accountability, joy, connection, kindness, possibilities, to loving continuous transformation.

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